

Descriptives - Motivation facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	22	.3323	.24796	.05287	.2223	.4422	.00	.70
	Tim	18	.2383	.16292	.03840	.1573	.3194	.00	.58
	Total	40	.2900	.21661	.03425	.2207	.3593	.00	.70
Recall	Abby	22	.3286	.24494	.05222	.2200	.4372	.00	.70
	Tim	18	.4456	.22706	.05352	.3326	.5585	.00	.80
	Total	40	.3813	.24134	.03816	.3041	.4584	.00	.80
FMeasure	Abby	22	.2152	.16512	.03520	.1420	.2884	.00	.63
	Tim	18	.2614	.12341	.02909	.2001	.3228	.00	.45
	Total	40	.2360	.14786	.02338	.1887	.2833	.00	.63
Duration	Abby	22	2041.5000	829.55913	176.86260	1673.6941	2409.3059	715.00	2805.00
	Tim	18	1684.5000	754.07678	177.73760	1309.5064	2059.4936	756.00	2760.00
	Total	40	1880.8500	806.70303	127.55095	1622.8539	2138.8461	715.00	2805.00
FirstActDet	Abby	22	717.2273	211.15711	45.01885	623.6055	810.8491	405.00	972.00
	Tim	18	565.6667	181.57481	42.79759	475.3716	655.9617	403.00	972.00
	Total	40	649.0250	210.26375	33.24562	581.7794	716.2706	403.00	972.00
LastActDet	Abby	22	1735.5455	901.79492	192.26332	1335.7120	2135.3789	325.00	2749.00
	Tim	18	1269.1111	860.32948	202.78160	841.2793	1696.9429	304.00	2749.00
	Total	40	1525.6500	903.19384	142.80748	1236.7946	1814.5054	304.00	2749.00
ProcDur	Abby	22	305.9545	335.60287	71.55077	157.1566	454.7525	11.00	1110.00
	Tim	18	415.3889	390.78596	92.10913	221.0556	609.7222	11.00	1546.00
	Total	40	355.2000	360.90728	57.06445	239.7763	470.6237	11.00	1546.00
FixRel	Abby	22	3.3268	.59844	.12759	3.0615	3.5922	2.25	4.35
	Tim	18	3.3933	.58044	.13681	3.1047	3.6820	2.64	4.35
	Total	40	3.3568	.58380	.09231	3.1700	3.5435	2.25	4.35
FixIrrel	Abby	22	5.5700	4.60246	.98125	3.5294	7.6106	2.66	17.70
	Tim	18	3.9083	1.39413	.32860	3.2151	4.6016	2.57	8.28
	Total	40	4.8223	3.59919	.56908	3.6712	5.9733	2.57	17.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	22	1161.5714	390.15097	83.18047	988.5881	1334.5546	525.29	1745.73
	Tim	18	945.3200	348.63053	82.17300	771.9501	1118.6899	497.00	1745.73
	Total	40	1064.2582	383.16424	60.58359	941.7164	1186.8001	497.00	1745.73
AvDurIrrelFix	Abby	22	985.4232	376.85429	80.34561	818.3353	1152.5110	521.48	1702.74
	Tim	18	1146.3583	447.12540	105.38847	924.0081	1368.7086	468.87	2152.04
	Total	40	1057.8440	412.54285	65.22875	925.9064	1189.7816	468.87	2152.04
TotSac	Abby	22	98.5455	11.32939	2.41543	93.5223	103.5686	74.00	113.00
	Tim	18	96.9444	9.44004	2.22504	92.2500	101.6389	75.00	111.00
	Total	40	97.8250	10.42159	1.64780	94.4920	101.1580	74.00	113.00
Sac2Key	Abby	22	59.2727	9.60249	2.04726	55.0152	63.5302	45.00	76.00
	Tim	18	57.0556	11.19597	2.63891	51.4879	62.6232	42.00	76.00
	Total	40	58.2750	10.27316	1.62433	54.9895	61.5605	42.00	76.00
AvAttention	Abby	22	.7182	.15318	.03266	.6503	.7861	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.8222	.18960	.04469	.7279	.9165	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.7650	.17621	.02786	.7086	.8214	.40	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	22	.6773	.21807	.04649	.5806	.7740	.40	1.00
	Tim	18	.7222	.19869	.04683	.6234	.8210	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.6975	.20815	.03291	.6309	.7641	.40	1.00
AvFam	Abby	22	.4182	.14683	.03130	.3531	.4833	.20	.70
	Tim	18	.5389	.13779	.03248	.4704	.6074	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4725	.15357	.02428	.4234	.5216	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	22	788.1364	107.91059	23.00661	740.2915	835.9812	631.00	1008.00
	Tim	18	805.9444	135.54008	31.94710	738.5419	873.3469	513.00	964.00
	Total	40	796.1500	119.82756	18.94640	757.8273	834.4727	513.00	1008.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	22	50.5027	24.28105	5.17674	39.7371	61.2683	15.92	87.27
	Tim	18	43.9656	19.76282	4.65814	34.1377	53.7934	15.92	83.83
	Total	40	47.2341	22.02193	4.41744	36.9374	57.5308	15.92	85.55

	Total	40	47.5610	22.32838	3.53043	40.4200	54.7020	15.92	87.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	22	48.1009	15.01563	3.20134	41.4434	54.7585	14.47	61.57
	Tim	18	30.4511	21.45375	5.05670	19.7824	41.1198	6.18	65.08
	Total	40	40.1585	20.02776	3.16667	33.7533	46.5637	6.18	65.08
NASA_MD	Abby	22	86.8182	16.29676	3.47448	79.5926	94.0438	60.00	100.00
	Tim	18	89.4444	11.49026	2.70828	83.7305	95.1584	60.00	100.00
	Total	40	88.0000	14.22349	2.24893	83.4511	92.5489	60.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	22	24.7727	17.14624	3.65559	17.1705	32.3749	10.00	75.00
	Tim	18	24.4444	15.32864	3.61300	16.8217	32.0672	10.00	70.00
	Total	40	24.6250	16.14785	2.55320	19.4607	29.7893	10.00	75.00
NASA_TD	Abby	22	49.3182	26.47080	5.64359	37.5817	61.0547	10.00	100.00
	Tim	18	55.8333	28.60738	6.74282	41.6072	70.0595	10.00	95.00
	Total	40	52.2500	27.29117	4.31511	43.5219	60.9781	10.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	22	62.0455	25.00757	5.33163	50.9577	73.1332	5.00	95.00
	Tim	18	58.6111	29.59559	6.97575	43.8936	73.3286	5.00	95.00
	Total	40	60.5000	26.86147	4.24717	51.9093	69.0907	5.00	95.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	22	76.5909	22.59300	4.81684	66.5737	86.6081	40.00	105.00
	Tim	18	78.3333	13.93261	3.28395	71.4048	85.2619	40.00	95.00
	Total	40	77.3750	18.98000	3.00100	71.3049	83.4451	40.00	105.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	22	75.6818	27.91550	5.95160	63.3048	88.0589	15.00	100.00
	Tim	18	71.3889	31.66022	7.46238	55.6446	87.1331	15.00	100.00
	Total	40	73.7500	29.34652	4.64009	64.3645	83.1355	15.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	22	72.4400	18.10473	3.85994	64.4128	80.4672	44.00	100.00
	Tim	18	74.2606	20.89066	4.92398	63.8719	84.6492	44.00	99.67
	Total	40	73.2593	19.17220	3.03139	67.1277	79.3908	44.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Motivation facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	2.067	1	36.466	.159
Recall	Welch	2.445	1	37.363	.126
FMeasure	Welch	1.026	1	37.735	.318
Duration	Welch	2.027	1	37.539	.163
FirstActDet	Welch	5.954	1	37.885	.059
LastActDet	Welch	2.786	1	37.059	.104
ProcDur	Welch	.880	1	33.756	.355
FixRel	Welch	.126	1	36.859	.724
FixIrrel	Welch	2.579	1	25.577	.121
AvDurRelFix	Welch	3.421	1	37.670	.072
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.475	1	33.377	.233
TotSac	Welch	.238	1	37.979	.629
Sac2Key	Welch	.441	1	33.730	.511
AvAttention	Welch	3.533	1	32.502	.069
AvMentWL	Welch	.464	1	37.520	.500
AvFam	Welch	7.161	1	37.240	.051
AvSCL	Welch	.205	1	32.195	.654
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.881	1	38.000	.354
HRVar_NN50	Welch	8.697	1	29.519	.006
NASA_MD	Welch	.355	1	37.273	.555
NASA_PD	Welch	.004	1	37.667	.949
NASA_TD	Welch	.549	1	35.183	.464
NASA_Performance	Welch	.153	1	33.428	.698
NASA_Effort	Welch	.089	1	35.567	.767
NASA_Frustration	Welch	.202	1	34.278	.656
NASA_Score	Welch	.085	1	33.938	.773

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Information processing facet									
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	20	.3495	.21239	.04749	.2501	.4489	.11	.70
	Tim	20	.2305	.20915	.04677	.1326	.3284	.00	.58
	Total	40	.2900	.21661	.03425	.2207	.3593	.00	.70
Recall	Abby	20	.3845	.22775	.05093	.2779	.4911	.00	.70
	Tim	20	.3780	.26013	.05817	.2563	.4997	.00	.80
	Total	40	.3813	.24134	.03816	.3041	.4584	.00	.80
FMeasure	Abby	20	.2674	.13371	.02990	.2048	.3299	.00	.63
	Tim	20	.2046	.15788	.03530	.1307	.2785	.00	.45
	Total	40	.2360	.14786	.02338	.1887	.2833	.00	.63
Duration	Abby	20	1463.1000	658.09973	147.15557	1155.0998	1771.1002	715.00	2805.00
	Tim	20	2298.6000	731.63871	163.59939	1956.1825	2641.0175	932.00	2760.00
	Total	40	1880.8500	806.70303	127.55095	1622.8539	2138.8461	715.00	2805.00
FirstActDet	Abby	20	529.9500	145.59261	32.55550	461.8106	598.0894	403.00	872.00
	Tim	20	768.1000	199.25147	44.55398	674.8474	861.3526	416.00	972.00
	Total	40	649.0250	210.26375	33.24562	581.7794	716.2706	403.00	972.00
LastActDet	Abby	20	885.0000	561.86944	125.63783	622.0370	1147.9630	304.00	2216.00
	Tim	20	2166.3000	703.34016	157.27164	1837.1267	2495.4733	858.00	2749.00
	Total	40	1525.6500	903.19384	142.80748	1236.7946	1814.5054	304.00	2749.00
ProcDur	Abby	20	578.1000	374.92173	83.83505	402.6312	753.5688	14.00	1546.00
	Tim	20	132.3000	148.99173	33.31556	62.5697	202.0303	11.00	348.00
	Total	40	355.2000	360.90728	57.06445	239.7763	470.6237	11.00	1546.00
FixRel	Abby	20	3.2975	.54742	.12241	3.0413	3.5537	2.64	4.35
	Tim	20	3.4160	.62651	.14009	3.1228	3.7092	2.25	4.35
	Total	40	3.3567	.58380	.09231	3.1700	3.5435	2.25	4.35
FixIrrel	Abby	20	6.5015	4.37245	.97771	4.4551	8.5479	2.57	17.70
	Tim	20	3.1430	1.23904	.27706	2.5631	3.7229	2.66	8.28
	Total	40	4.8223	3.59919	.56908	3.6712	5.9733	2.57	17.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	20	782.6060	187.82199	41.99827	694.7026	870.5094	497.00	1194.29
	Tim	20	1345.9105	314.75923	70.38230	1198.5986	1493.2224	699.71	1745.73
	Total	40	1064.2582	383.16424	60.58359	941.7164	1186.8001	497.00	1745.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	20	1234.6230	340.45280	76.12756	1075.2862	1393.9598	859.87	2152.04
	Tim	20	881.0650	409.44031	91.55364	689.4410	1072.6890	468.87	1701.22
	Total	40	1057.8440	412.54285	65.22875	925.9064	1189.7816	468.87	2152.04
TotSac	Abby	20	94.2500	11.82715	2.64463	88.7147	99.7853	74.00	113.00
	Tim	20	101.4000	7.49315	1.67552	97.8931	104.9069	90.00	111.00
	Total	40	97.8250	10.42159	1.64780	94.4920	101.1580	74.00	113.00
Sac2Key	Abby	20	55.3500	11.03714	2.46798	50.1845	60.5155	42.00	75.00
	Tim	20	61.2000	8.76356	1.95959	57.0985	65.3015	43.00	76.00
	Total	40	58.2750	10.27316	1.62433	54.9895	61.5605	42.00	76.00
AvAttention	Abby	20	.8300	.15252	.03411	.7586	.9014	.60	1.00
	Tim	20	.7000	.17770	.03974	.6168	.7832	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.7650	.17621	.02786	.7086	.8214	.40	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	20	.8150	.17252	.03858	.7343	.8957	.50	1.00
	Tim	20	.5800	.17351	.03880	.4988	.6612	.40	.90
	Total	40	.6975	.20815	.03291	.6309	.7641	.40	1.00
AvFam	Abby	20	.5100	.12096	.02705	.4534	.5666	.30	.70
	Tim	20	.4350	.17554	.03925	.3528	.5172	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4725	.15357	.02428	.4234	.5216	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	20	799.2500	137.54612	30.75625	734.8764	863.6236	513.00	1008.00
	Tim	20	793.0500	102.63449	22.94977	745.0156	841.0844	683.00	964.00
	Total	40	796.1500	119.82756	18.94640	757.8273	834.4727	513.00	1008.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	20	51.4520	21.78812	4.87197	41.2548	61.6492	15.92	87.27
	Tim	20	43.6700	22.73230	5.08310	33.0310	54.3090	15.92	80.96
	Total	40	47.5610	22.26021	4.97754	37.1429	57.9791	15.92	84.11

	Total	40	47.5610	22.32838	3.53043	40.4200	54.7020	15.92	87.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	20	50.5685	13.89822	3.10774	44.0639	57.0731	7.81	61.57
	Tim	20	29.7485	20.05067	4.48347	20.3645	39.1325	6.18	65.08
	Total	40	40.1585	20.02776	3.16667	33.7533	46.5637	6.18	65.08
NASA_MD	Abby	20	93.7500	8.40974	1.88047	89.8141	97.6859	75.00	100.00
	Tim	20	82.2500	16.58114	3.70766	74.4898	90.0102	60.00	100.00
	Total	40	88.0000	14.22349	2.24893	83.4511	92.5489	60.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	20	27.7500	22.03317	4.92677	17.4382	38.0618	10.00	75.00
	Tim	20	21.5000	5.40468	1.20852	18.9705	24.0295	15.00	30.00
	Total	40	24.6250	16.14785	2.55320	19.4607	29.7893	10.00	75.00
NASA_TD	Abby	20	56.2500	32.35799	7.23547	41.1060	71.3940	10.00	100.00
	Tim	20	48.2500	21.16819	4.73335	38.3430	58.1570	30.00	95.00
	Total	40	52.2500	27.29117	4.31511	43.5219	60.9781	10.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	20	54.5000	30.30112	6.77554	40.3186	68.6814	5.00	85.00
	Tim	20	66.5000	22.07046	4.93511	56.1707	76.8293	25.00	95.00
	Total	40	60.5000	26.86147	4.24717	51.9093	69.0907	5.00	95.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	20	83.2500	12.90400	2.88542	77.2107	89.2893	60.00	105.00
	Tim	20	71.5000	22.36656	5.00132	61.0321	81.9679	40.00	95.00
	Total	40	77.3750	18.98000	3.00100	71.3049	83.4451	40.00	105.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	20	81.5000	24.17589	5.40589	70.1853	92.8147	15.00	100.00
	Tim	20	66.0000	32.50911	7.26926	50.7853	81.2147	15.00	100.00
	Total	40	73.7500	29.34652	4.64009	64.3645	83.1355	15.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	20	79.7680	17.93604	4.01062	71.3737	88.1623	44.00	100.00
	Tim	20	66.7505	18.53655	4.14490	58.0751	75.4259	44.00	99.67
	Total	40	73.2593	19.17220	3.03139	67.1277	79.3908	44.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Information processing facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	3.188	1	37.991	.042
Recall	Welch	.007	1	37.347	.933
FMeasure	Welch	1.840	1	36.997	.183
Duration	Welch	14.417	1	37.581	.052
FirstActDet	Welch	18.626	1	34.788	.062
LastActDet	Welch	40.517	1	36.232	.064
ProcDur	Welch	24.420	1	24.855	.051
FixRel	Welch	.406	1	37.329	.528
FixIrrel	Welch	10.923	1	22.032	.003
AvDurRelFix	Welch	47.236	1	31.008	.000
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	8.817	1	36.776	.005
TotSac	Welch	5.216	1	32.136	.059
Sac2Key	Welch	3.446	1	36.143	.072
AvAttention	Welch	6.163	1	37.146	.018
AvMentWL	Welch	18.449	1	37.999	.000
AvFam	Welch	2.475	1	33.723	.125
AvSCL	Welch	.026	1	35.151	.873
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	1.222	1	37.932	.276
HRVar_NN50	Welch	14.566	1	33.833	.001
NASA_MD	Welch	7.652	1	28.168	.299
NASA_PD	Welch	1.518	1	21.278	.231
NASA_TD	Welch	.856	1	32.745	.362
NASA_Performance	Welch	2.049	1	34.732	.161
NASA_Effort	Welch	4.141	1	30.387	.051
NASA_Frustration	Welch	2.928	1	35.093	.096
NASA_Score	Welch	5.094	1	37.959	.060

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Self-efficacy facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	14	.3814	.24197	.06467	.2417	.5211	.03	.70
	Tim	26	.2408	.18853	.03697	.1646	.3169	.00	.58
	Total	40	.2900	.21661	.03425	.2207	.3593	.00	.70
Recall	Abby	14	.3271	.20529	.05487	.2086	.4457	.00	.70
	Tim	26	.4104	.25774	.05055	.3063	.5145	.00	.80
	Total	40	.3813	.24134	.03816	.3041	.4584	.00	.80
FMeasure	Abby	14	.2628	.17261	.04613	.1631	.3625	.00	.63
	Tim	26	.2216	.13414	.02631	.1674	.2757	.00	.40
	Total	40	.2360	.14786	.02338	.1887	.2833	.00	.63
Duration	Abby	14	1721.0000	755.36990	201.88110	1284.8624	2157.1376	756.00	2805.00
	Tim	26	1966.9231	834.55573	163.66985	1629.8387	2304.0074	715.00	2805.00
	Total	40	1880.8500	806.70303	127.55095	1622.8539	2138.8461	715.00	2805.00
FirstActDet	Abby	14	596.2143	220.08676	58.82066	469.1400	723.2886	403.00	972.00
	Tim	26	677.4615	203.41647	39.89325	595.2998	759.6232	405.00	972.00
	Total	40	649.0250	210.26375	33.24562	581.7794	716.2706	403.00	972.00
LastActDet	Abby	14	1164.7857	744.64335	199.01431	734.8414	1594.7300	325.00	2412.00
	Tim	26	1719.9615	933.83902	183.14090	1342.7758	2097.1473	304.00	2749.00
	Total	40	1525.6500	903.19384	142.80748	1236.7946	1814.5054	304.00	2749.00
ProcDur	Abby	14	556.2143	412.14769	110.15110	318.2473	794.1813	14.00	1546.00
	Tim	26	246.9615	282.93851	55.48881	132.6802	361.2429	11.00	1110.00
	Total	40	355.2000	360.90728	57.06445	239.7763	470.6237	11.00	1546.00
FixRel	Abby	14	3.2986	.56277	.15041	2.9736	3.6235	2.64	4.35
	Tim	26	3.3881	.60338	.11833	3.1444	3.6318	2.25	4.35
	Total	40	3.3568	.58380	.09231	3.1700	3.5435	2.25	4.35
FixIrrel	Abby	14	5.7564	4.05860	1.08471	3.4131	8.0998	2.57	17.70
	Tim	26	4.3192	3.30016	.64721	2.9863	5.6522	2.66	17.70
	Total	40	4.8223	3.59919	.56908	3.6712	5.9733	2.57	17.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	14	895.9643	342.61262	91.56707	698.1457	1093.7829	497.00	1745.73
	Tim	26	1154.8781	378.93342	74.31496	1001.8236	1307.9326	636.07	1745.73
	Total	40	1064.2583	383.16424	60.58359	941.7164	1186.8001	497.00	1745.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	14	1263.8829	435.57512	116.41235	1012.3893	1515.3764	524.65	2152.04
	Tim	26	946.9000	360.92591	70.78339	801.1189	1092.6811	468.87	1701.22
	Total	40	1057.8440	412.54285	65.22875	925.9064	1189.7816	468.87	2152.04
TotSac	Abby	14	96.3571	11.41259	3.05014	89.7677	102.9466	77.00	113.00
	Tim	26	98.6154	9.99230	1.95965	94.5794	102.6514	74.00	111.00
	Total	40	97.8250	10.42159	1.64780	94.4920	101.1580	74.00	113.00
Sac2Key	Abby	14	54.3571	10.42635	2.78656	48.3371	60.3771	42.00	73.00
	Tim	26	60.3846	9.74095	1.91036	56.4502	64.3191	43.00	76.00
	Total	40	58.2750	10.27316	1.62433	54.9895	61.5605	42.00	76.00
AvAttention	Abby	14	.8857	.10271	.02745	.8264	.9450	.70	1.00
	Tim	26	.7000	.17436	.03419	.6296	.7704	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.7650	.17621	.02786	.7086	.8214	.40	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	14	.7571	.18277	.04885	.6516	.8627	.50	1.00
	Tim	26	.6654	.21715	.04259	.5777	.7531	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.6975	.20815	.03291	.6309	.7641	.40	1.00
AvFam	Abby	14	.5071	.11411	.03050	.4413	.5730	.30	.70
	Tim	26	.4538	.17025	.03339	.3851	.5226	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4725	.15357	.02428	.4234	.5216	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	14	739.0000	138.78761	37.09255	658.8664	819.1336	513.00	943.00
	Tim	26	826.9231	97.82307	19.18468	787.4115	866.4347	683.00	1008.00
	Total	40	796.1500	119.82756	18.94640	757.8273	834.4727	513.00	1008.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	14	50.7029	25.45063	6.80197	36.0081	65.3976	15.92	87.27
	Tim	26	45.8692	20.79475	4.07819	37.4700	54.2684	15.92	80.96

	Total	40	47.5610	22.32838	3.53043	40.4200	54.7020	15.92	87.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	14	33.5336	22.81421	6.09735	20.3610	46.7061	6.18	65.08
	Tim	26	43.7258	17.81198	3.49322	36.5314	50.9202	7.81	61.57
	Total	40	40.1585	20.02776	3.16667	33.7533	46.5637	6.18	65.08
NASA_MD	Abby	14	96.4286	7.70329	2.05879	91.9808	100.8763	75.00	100.00
	Tim	26	83.4615	14.95120	2.93217	77.4226	89.5005	60.00	100.00
	Total	40	88.0000	14.22349	2.24893	83.4511	92.5489	60.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	14	29.6429	24.13618	6.45066	15.7070	43.5787	10.00	75.00
	Tim	26	21.9231	9.06388	1.77757	18.2621	25.5841	10.00	55.00
	Total	40	24.6250	16.14785	2.55320	19.4607	29.7893	10.00	75.00
NASA_TD	Abby	14	59.2857	31.85648	8.51400	40.8923	77.6791	10.00	100.00
	Tim	26	48.4615	24.32156	4.76985	38.6378	58.2852	10.00	95.00
	Total	40	52.2500	27.29117	4.31511	43.5219	60.9781	10.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	14	63.2143	25.16157	6.72471	48.6864	77.7421	5.00	85.00
	Tim	26	59.0385	28.10762	5.51236	47.6855	70.3914	5.00	95.00
	Total	40	60.5000	26.86147	4.24717	51.9093	69.0907	5.00	95.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	14	86.7857	13.95145	3.72868	78.7304	94.8410	60.00	105.00
	Tim	26	72.3077	19.60769	3.84538	64.3880	80.2274	40.00	95.00
	Total	40	77.3750	18.98000	3.00100	71.3049	83.4451	40.00	105.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	14	90.0000	15.31716	4.09368	81.1561	98.8439	55.00	100.00
	Tim	26	65.0000	31.52777	6.18310	52.2657	77.7343	15.00	100.00
	Total	40	73.7500	29.34652	4.64009	64.3645	83.1355	15.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	14	83.8814	14.65535	3.91681	75.4197	92.3432	50.67	100.00
	Tim	26	67.5396	19.09243	3.74433	59.8280	75.2512	44.00	99.67
	Total	40	73.2593	19.17220	3.03139	67.1277	79.3908	44.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Self-efficacy facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	3.565	1	21.683	.042
Recall	Welch	1.245	1	32.323	.273
FMeasure	Welch	.603	1	21.640	.446
Duration	Welch	.895	1	29.156	.035
FirstActDet	Welch	1.307	1	24.963	.264
LastActDet	Welch	4.214	1	32.297	.058
ProcDur	Welch	6.287	1	19.773	.052
FixRel	Welch	.219	1	28.414	.644
FixIrrel	Welch	1.295	1	22.426	.027
AvDurRelFix	Welch	4.820	1	29.182	.036
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	5.413	1	22.771	.029
TotSac	Welch	.388	1	23.835	.539
Sac2Key	Welch	3.183	1	25.197	.086
AvAttention	Welch	17.938	1	37.586	.000
AvMentWL	Welch	2.005	1	30.968	.017
AvFam	Welch	1.389	1	35.969	.246
AvSCL	Welch	4.433	1	20.136	.058
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.371	1	22.513	.548
HRVar_NN50	Welch	2.104	1	21.718	.161
NASA_MD	Welch	13.099	1	37.976	.001
NASA_PD	Welch	1.331	1	15.004	.267
NASA_TD	Welch	1.230	1	21.348	.028
NASA_Performance	Welch	.231	1	29.430	.635
NASA_Effort	Welch	7.306	1	34.856	.011
NASA_Frustration	Welch	11.366	1	37.766	.002
NASA_Score	Welch	9.095	1	33.200	.051

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Risk facet									
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	22	.3750	.24855	.05299	.2648	.4852	.00	.70
	Tim	18	.1861	.10268	.02420	.1351	.2372	.02	.37
	Total	40	.2900	.21661	.03425	.2207	.3593	.00	.70
Recall	Abby	22	.2527	.20112	.04288	.1636	.3419	.00	.70
	Tim	18	.5383	.19015	.04482	.4438	.6329	.13	.80
	Total	40	.3813	.24134	.03816	.3041	.4584	.00	.80
FMeasure	Abby	22	.2278	.17705	.03775	.1493	.3063	.00	.63
	Tim	18	.2460	.10602	.02499	.1933	.2987	.04	.40
	Total	40	.2360	.14786	.02338	.1887	.2833	.00	.63
Duration	Abby	22	2343.3182	721.16040	153.75191	2023.5736	2663.0628	715.00	2805.00
	Tim	18	1315.6111	485.21083	114.36529	1074.3214	1556.9008	756.00	2230.00
	Total	40	1880.8500	806.70303	127.55095	1622.8539	2138.8461	715.00	2805.00
FirstActDet	Abby	22	778.8182	193.62129	41.28020	692.9713	864.6651	405.00	972.00
	Tim	18	490.3889	81.65720	19.24679	449.7817	530.9961	403.00	690.00
	Total	40	649.0250	210.26375	33.24562	581.7794	716.2706	403.00	972.00
LastActDet	Abby	22	2042.5000	837.83251	178.62649	1671.0259	2413.9741	325.00	2749.00
	Tim	18	893.9444	485.88881	114.52509	652.3176	1135.5713	304.00	2216.00
	Total	40	1525.6500	903.19384	142.80748	1236.7946	1814.5054	304.00	2749.00
ProcDur	Abby	22	300.8182	332.54139	70.89806	153.3776	448.2588	11.00	1110.00
	Tim	18	421.6667	392.05837	92.40904	226.7006	616.6327	13.00	1546.00
	Total	40	355.2000	360.90728	57.06445	239.7763	470.6237	11.00	1546.00
FixRel	Abby	22	3.4755	.58695	.12514	3.2152	3.7357	2.64	4.35
	Tim	18	3.2117	.56194	.13245	2.9322	3.4911	2.25	4.35
	Total	40	3.3568	.58380	.09231	3.1700	3.5435	2.25	4.35
FixIrrel	Abby	22	6.9409	4.49403	.95813	2.9484	7.9335	2.66	17.70
	Tim	18	4.6772	2.17474	.51259	3.5957	5.7587	2.57	10.39
	Total	40	4.8223	3.59919	.56908	3.6712	5.9733	2.57	17.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	22	862.2294	259.49127	61.16268	733.1875	991.2714	497.00	1477.00
	Tim	18	1229.5545	393.11254	83.81187	1055.2582	1403.8509	525.29	1745.73
	Total	40	1064.2582	383.16424	60.58359	941.7164	1186.8001	497.00	1745.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	22	1135.8233	424.17589	99.97922	924.8856	1346.7610	468.87	2152.04
	Tim	18	994.0427	401.17312	85.53040	816.1725	1171.9129	524.65	1702.74
	Total	40	995.0427	412.54285	65.22875	925.9064	1189.7816	468.87	2152.04
TotSac	Abby	22	99.7273	9.68151	2.06410	95.4347	104.0198	81.00	113.00
	Tim	18	95.5000	11.08921	2.61375	89.9855	101.0145	74.00	111.00
	Total	40	97.8250	10.42159	1.64780	94.4920	101.1580	74.00	113.00
Sac2Key	Abby	22	61.7273	8.29906	1.76937	58.0477	65.4069	46.00	76.00
	Tim	18	54.0556	11.07978	2.61153	48.5457	59.5654	42.00	75.00
	Total	40	58.2750	10.27316	1.62433	54.9895	61.5605	42.00	76.00
AvAttention	Abby	22	.7409	.14362	.03062	.6772	.8046	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.7944	.20996	.04949	.6900	.8989	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.7650	.17621	.02786	.7086	.8214	.40	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	22	.6227	.20455	.04361	.5320	.7134	.40	1.00
	Tim	18	.7889	.17786	.04192	.7004	.8773	.40	1.00
	Total	40	.6975	.20815	.03291	.6309	.7641	.40	1.00
AvFam	Abby	22	.4273	.15791	.03367	.3573	.4973	.20	.70
	Tim	18	.5278	.13198	.03111	.4621	.5934	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4725	.15357	.02428	.4234	.5216	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	22	766.0909	94.47293	20.14170	724.2040	807.9779	631.00	1008.00
	Tim	18	832.8889	138.98493	32.75906	763.7733	902.0045	513.00	964.00
	Total	40	796.1500	119.82756	18.94640	757.8273	834.4727	513.00	1008.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	22	47.6668	25.86045	5.51347	36.2009	59.1327	15.92	87.27
	Tim	18	47.4317	17.82124	4.20051	38.5694	56.2940	15.92	83.83
	Total	40	47.5492	21.84084	3.85700	37.3851	57.7134	15.92	85.55

	Total	40	47.5610	22.32838	3.53043	40.4200	54.7020	15.92	87.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	22	49.0418	14.79359	3.15400	42.4827	55.6009	14.47	61.57
	Tim	18	29.3011	20.56480	4.84717	19.0745	39.5277	6.18	65.08
	Total	40	40.1585	20.02776	3.16667	33.7533	46.5637	6.18	65.08
NASA_MD	Abby	22	86.8182	17.83158	3.80171	78.9121	94.7243	60.00	100.00
	Tim	18	89.4444	8.20489	1.93391	85.3642	93.5246	75.00	100.00
	Total	40	88.0000	14.22349	2.24893	83.4511	92.5489	60.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	22	23.1818	17.15097	3.65660	15.5775	30.7861	10.00	75.00
	Tim	18	26.3889	15.12745	3.56558	18.8662	33.9116	10.00	70.00
	Total	40	24.6250	16.14785	2.55320	19.4607	29.7893	10.00	75.00
NASA_TD	Abby	22	62.9545	27.10909	5.77968	40.9350	64.9740	10.00	100.00
	Tim	18	51.3889	28.27416	6.66428	37.3285	65.4493	10.00	95.00
	Total	40	52.2500	27.29117	4.31511	43.5219	60.9781	10.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	22	59.3182	20.19521	4.30563	50.3641	68.2722	20.00	85.00
	Tim	18	61.9444	33.87429	7.98425	45.0992	78.7897	5.00	95.00
	Total	40	60.5000	26.86147	4.24717	51.9093	69.0907	5.00	95.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	22	76.5909	24.41635	5.20558	65.7653	87.4165	40.00	105.00
	Tim	18	78.3333	9.39336	2.21404	73.6621	83.0045	60.00	95.00
	Total	40	77.3750	18.98000	3.00100	71.3049	83.4451	40.00	105.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	22	85.2273	14.67726	3.12920	78.7197	91.7348	60.00	100.00
	Tim	18	59.7222	36.48014	8.59845	41.5811	77.8634	15.00	100.00
	Total	40	73.7500	29.34652	4.64009	64.3645	83.1355	15.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	22	77.8036	15.02007	3.20229	71.1441	84.4632	60.67	100.00
	Tim	18	67.7050	22.47622	5.29770	56.5278	78.8822	44.00	99.67
	Total	40	73.2593	19.17220	3.03139	67.1277	79.3908	44.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Risk facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	10.513	1	29.110	.003
Recall	Welch	21.202	1	37.161	.000
FMeasure	Welch	.161	1	35.110	.690
Duration	Welch	28.764	1	36.764	.051
FirstActDet	Welch	40.102	1	29.406	.000
LastActDet	Welch	29.300	1	34.593	.052
ProcDur	Welch	1.077	1	33.506	.307
FixRel	Welch	2.096	1	37.018	.156
FixIrrel	Welch	.059	1	31.549	.048
AvDurRelFix	Welch	12.534	1	36.526	.001
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.161	1	35.567	.029
TotSac	Welch	1.611	1	34.084	.213
Sac2Key	Welch	5.915	1	30.916	.521
AvAttention	Welch	.846	1	29.060	.365
AvMentWL	Welch	7.545	1	37.834	.059
AvFam	Welch	4.808	1	37.973	.055
AvSCL	Welch	3.017	1	28.935	.093
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.001	1	37.039	.973
HRVar_NN50	Welch	11.653	1	30.078	.061
NASA_MD	Welch	.379	1	30.732	.543
NASA_PD	Welch	.394	1	37.755	.534
NASA_TD	Welch	.032	1	35.797	.049
NASA_Performance	Welch	.084	1	26.510	.774
NASA_Effort	Welch	.095	1	28.147	.760
NASA_Frustration	Welch	7.770	1	21.496	.011
NASA_Score	Welch	2.661	1	28.601	.114

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Learning style facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.025	1	37.993	.875
Recall	Welch	.093	1	37.345	.763
FMeasure	Welch	.482	1	37.839	.492
Duration	Welch	2.065	1	37.509	.159
FirstActDet	Welch	3.065	1	37.882	.048
LastActDet	Welch	2.779	1	37.297	.104
ProcDur	Welch	.825	1	32.708	.370
FixRel	Welch	4.093	1	37.740	.050
FixIrrel	Welch	.257	1	37.945	.615
AvDurRelFix	Welch	1.860	1	34.352	.181
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	.023	1	37.906	.879
TotSac	Welch	.099	1	36.121	.755
Sac2Key	Welch	2.727	1	36.150	.107
AvAttention	Welch	.126	1	33.756	.725
AvMentWL	Welch	2.652	1	37.616	.112
AvFam	Welch	3.240	1	37.930	.080
AvSCL	Welch	.436	1	31.428	.514
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.255	1	37.701	.616
HRVar_NN50	Welch	6.074	1	37.571	.084
NASA_MD	Welch	1.001	1	32.567	.324
NASA_PD	Welch	3.094	1	26.083	.090
NASA_TD	Welch	1.355	1	35.831	.252
NASA_Performance	Welch	3.547	1	37.979	.067
NASA_Effort	Welch	1.087	1	35.178	.304
NASA_Frustration	Welch	1.420	1	31.469	.242
NASA_Score	Welch	.202	1	35.886	.656

a. Asymptotically F distributed.